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TITLE: Assessing influence of water table on slope stability during construction.

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Abstract

During construction, especially of structures that have deep excavations, assessing the influence of water table on slope stability should be a primary objective in order to ensure safety. High water tables affect construction works in terms of cost and time incurred during mitigation of possible failure. Mechanical properties of soil were studied using laboratory tests and review of secondary data. The results showed that water table negatively affected stability by reducing the factor of safety and therefore proper groundwater investigations and sustainable slope stabilization mechanisms like geo nailing, use of piles or sub-surface drainage systems are required to improve stability based on slope conditions of each site.

Declaration

I, BRUCE AMANYA hereby declare that this is my original work, is not plagiarized and has not been submitted any other institution for any award.

X

Bruce Amany
Author

Signature and Date

Dedication

To my dad Godfrey and my mom Molly, for all that you have done for me.

Acknowledgements

I would like to acknowledge The Almighty God by whose grace I was able to complete this physically and academically challenging study.

I am much indebted to the people that I interacted with during this research for their insights, advice, critiques and criticisms formed the spring for encouragement and resilience to finish this work. Our shared experiences have greatly formed part of my not only academic life but also in the social terms as you have helped me torch my highly anticipated career life journey ahead.

I wish to express my thanks Private Sector Foundation Uganda for allowing me conduct this study on their site at Plot 1 Baskerville Avenue along Roscoe road and further provided the necessary information for review, Teclab Engineers Laboratory who offered laboratory services and whose advice, comments and guidance helped me a lot to acquire skills and knowledge.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

UBFC	-	Uganda Business Facilitation Centre
TP	-	Trial Point
SPT	-	Standard Penetration Test
BH	-	Borehole
WT	-	Water Table
FoS	-	Factor of Safety
Cv	-	Coefficient of Consolidation
Cc	-	Coefficient of Compressibility
M	-	Meters
LL	-	Liquid Limit
Kg	-	Kilogram
BS	-	British Standard

1.0 GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 Topic

Assessing the influence of water table on slope stability during construction.

1.2 Background

Many slope failures around the world, particularly in regions with residual soils, occur due to changes in unsaturated soil condition as a result of frequent heavy rainfalls. Matric suction or negative pore-water pressure plays an important role in the stability of these slopes (Fredlund and Rahardjo 1993) A deep groundwater table and a significant thickness of unsaturated zone above the groundwater table are general characteristics of steep residual soil slopes. In tropical and subtropical areas, rainfall-induced slope failures are closely related to the properties of the soil, the geometry of the slope, the position of groundwater table, and certain environmental factors vegetation and weathering effects. Previous research works have shown that rainfall is the main contributing factor of slope failures in Singapore (Brand 1984; Tan et al. 1987; Chatterjea 1989; Lim et al. 1996; Toll et al. 1999; Rahardjo et al. 2007a, b)

Statistics on groundwater use in Sub-Saharan Africa are sparse and incomplete, although very high dependence for rural domestic water-supply, small-scale livelihoods and livestock rearing is undisputable. The introduction of deep drilling rigs and pumping plant from the 1970s enabled the area under human settlement to be extended in response to increasing population and growing pressure on riparian land. (Albert Tuinhof et al. 2011)

In Uganda, construction problems related to high water table affect road projects especially across flood plains but also construction works especially for deep excavations. Several methods are used for example sheet piling, soil nailing and use of gabions to improve soil's ability to resist shearing.

The site area climate is wet tropical with temperatures ranging from 15 to 29°C. As is the case with all other areas in this region, Kampala experiences two wet seasons from March to May and in August to December when the major rains are received. The mean annual rainfall is between 1125mm and 1350mm. (en.wikipedia.org)

The site has a high-water table at the depth of 10.5 m from the surface which has affected the soil properties and had a negative effect on soil's ability to resist shearing leading to slope failure. (Nammuli Veronica, 2016)

1.3 Problem Statement

UBFC Construction site in Kololo has a high-water table at a depth of 10.5m from the ground surface which has affected construction works in terms of cost and time. This is also related to high slope instability that has caused slope failure and its associated consequences like interruption of traffic and risk of occupational hazards. Several methods to ensure soil stability have been applied, however all have failed to a large extent. Water has a negative effect on soil's ability to resist shearing, which leads to slope failure. An increase in pore pressure leads to a decrease in effective stress (σ'). Because σ' governs the soil's strength characteristics, the presence of water leads to decreased soil shear strength. Controlling groundwater in the slope area is a fundamental way to increase the resistance to shear failure.

1.4 Objectives of the study

Main Objective

- To assess the influence of water table on slope stability.

Specific Objectives

- To determine the mechanical properties of soil that affect soil stability (Bearing Capacity, shear strength and Consolidation)
- To determine the relationship between soil strength and ground water quantity.
- To design a slope stabilization mechanism.

1.5 Research Questions

1. What mechanical properties of soil affect soil stability?
2. What is the relationship between soil strength and ground water quantity?
3. What suitable slope stabilization mechanism can be applied?

1.6 Justification of the study

Slope Stabilization is considered as the basic requirement of any foundation construction project. The purpose of the slope stabilization is to prevent the rain impact, run off velocity of the surface and also the soil erosion. It increases the shear strength of a soil and/or control the shrink-swell properties of a soil, thus improving the load bearing capacity of a slope to support foundations. The purpose of this study is to determine effective methods of stabilizing slopes and recommend slope stabilization methods for common site conditions. The project recommends simple,

effective methods of stabilizing at-risk sites and repair options for common, recurring slope failures. There is currently no guide to stabilize slopes of the scale typically seen at UBFC site in Kololo. Therefore, slope failures can block roads, pose safety hazards, and introduce preventable maintenance costs. While there is no single stabilization method appropriate for all situations, several methods have proven effective.

1.7 Significance

The purpose for my research is to assess the influence of water table on soil stability during construction. The purpose of this project is to create a model for reference about the same problem faced in other places or close fields of work and study irrigation by focusing on locally maintained slopes requiring reoccurring maintenance in Kololo. This study addresses the need to provide a consistent, logical approach to slope stabilization that is founded in geotechnical research and experience and applies to common slope failures. I used input from site engineers, case studies from investigations throughout the world, and a parametric study of slope stability modeling parameters to develop stabilization recommendations.

1.8 Scope of the Study

The scope of this research is as follows;

- Recovering both disturbed and undisturbed samples
- Registering of ground water occurrence

- Laboratory Testing of the samples recovered to establish relationship with ground water levels and amount
- Proposition of suitable solution (if water table affects the soil properties)
- Preparation of a research report.

Location:

The site investigated is located at Plot 1, Baskerville Avenue along Roscoe Road, Kampala District. Some neighbors of the site are the Burundi Embassy, and City High School. The site housed an old structure and was not habited. It is intended to house Uganda Business Facilitation Centre.

Figure 1: Satellite Image of the geographical site location (Google maps)

1.9 Limitations of the Study

During the field study of the site, I noted that the site was fully designed to accommodate the structure which hindered proper collection of soil samples to use analysis except for the collapsed retaining wall surface. Furthermore, Since the superstructure has covered the specific geographic positions of field exploration for BH 1 and BH 2, the soil samples obtained for the Undrained Triaxial test were obtained from the collapsed retaining wall whose soil mass is left exposed.

This research therefore borrows factual data of both strength laboratory tests and that were recorded through the Geotechnical report (Plot 1 Baskerville Avenue Geotechnical Investigations Services Final Report Ref: 2016/137) prepared by TECLAB Limited who were contracted by SSENTONGO & PARTNERS in September 2016. The permission to use the data and the report itself was therefore warranted as per the letter in Appendix and the report is attached as Annex 1.

Conceptual Framework

The study shall follow a framework as shown in the figure below.

Figure 2: Conceptual flow framework for the study.

According to the above diagram, the study shall commence with study of parameters of the first objective i.e. mechanical properties of the soil using both primary and secondary data. The analysis of this data will be aided by computer aided software to establish their relationship with soil stability. I shall thereafter assess the relevance of the result to the study before proceeding to objective two to study the relationship between water table and soil stability from the primary data secured in objective 1.

I shall there after analyze the data taking several assumptions and theories in place, for example all seepage within the soil mass is artesian in nature based on the influence of rainfall but also pressure from nearby structural loads. This will be used to generate environmental models to simulate ideal artesian seepage conditions and underground drainage flow as proposed solution for stability improvement.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

To provide slope stabilization recommendations, researchers needed to establish a background understanding of slope stability and stabilization methods.

Slope stability is typically quantified with a factor of safety (FS). Stabilizing a slope involves increasing the Factor of Safety. The Factor of Safety is the ratio of shear strength to the required shear strength for equilibrium along a given potential failure surface, as shown in Equation 1.

(Eqn. 1) Factor of Safety = *insitu* shear strength / Shear stress required for sliding

Fundamentally, there are two ways to increase the Factor of Safety and increase slope stability: introduce more stabilizing forces (increase capacity) or limit driving forces (decrease demand). Academic research, standard engineering practice, and worldwide experience have produced many slope stabilization methods; most fit into four categories: controlling groundwater with drainage, using surface cover, excavating and regrading, and adding reinforcing support structures. Water has a negative effect on soil's ability to resist shearing, which leads to slope failure. An increase in pore pressure leads to a decrease in effective stress (σ'). Because σ' governs the soil's strength characteristics, the presence of water leads to decreased soil shear strength. Controlling groundwater in the slope area is a fundamental way to increase the resistance to shear failure. (Saftner and Investigator, 2017)

All soils are permeable materials, water being free to flow through the interconnected pores between the solid particles. The pressure of the pore water is measured relative to atmospheric pressure and the level at which the pressure is

atmospheric (i.e. zero) is defined as the water table (WT) or the phreatic surface. Below the water table the soil is assumed to be fully saturated, although it is likely that, due to the presence of small volumes of entrapped air, the degree of saturation will be marginally below 100%. The level of the water table changes according to climatic conditions but the level can change also as a consequence of constructional operations. A perched water table can occur locally, contained by soil of low permeability, above the normal water table level. Artesian conditions can exist if an inclined soil layer of high permeability is confined locally by an overlying layer of low permeability; the pressure in the artesian layer is governed not by the local water table level but by a higher water table level at a distant location where the layer is unconfined. Below the water table the pore water may be static, the hydrostatic pressure depending on the depth below the water table, or may be seeping through the soil under hydraulic gradient: this chapter is concerned with the second case. Bernoulli's theorem applies to the pore water but seepage velocities in soils are normally so small that velocity head can be neglected.

$$h = \frac{u}{\gamma_w} + z$$

Where h is the total head, u the pore water pressure, γ_w the unit weight of water (9.8 kN/m³) and z the elevation head above a chosen datum. Above the water table, water can be held at negative pressure by capillary tension; the smaller the size of the pores the higher the water can rise above the water table. The capillary rise tends to be irregular due to the random pore sizes occurring in a soil. The soil can be almost completely saturated in the lower part of the capillary zone but in general the degree of saturation decreases with height. When water percolates

through the soil from the surface towards the water table some of this water can be held by surface tension around the points of contact between particles. The negative pressure of water held above the water table results in attractive forces between the particles: this attraction is referred to as soil suction and is a function of pore size and water content. (Craig, 2013)

Angle of Repose

The strength of a soil is critical to civil engineering work. Almost all built structures rest on soil foundations, making strong soils as foundations very important. Cohesionless soil strength depends on the soil's mineral type, particle size, and particle shape. This demonstrates the role of particle shape in the soil's strength. When evaluating the building site for the project, the geotechnical engineer considered the shape of the soil particles. More angular soil particles develop higher stresses at the points of contact with each other, thus generating higher strength. Smoother particles produce less stress. Higher stress makes it harder for the soil particles to move around and slide downhill.

Earlier studies of factors determining subaerial angles of repose of loose material have produced diverse results. In order to obtain dependable information for use in geomorphic investigations a controlled experimental study was undertaken. Results show that the angle of repose varies (1) inversely with size of fragments in perfectly sorted materials, but directly in those imperfectly sorted; (2) inversely with density of fragments; (3) directly with their angularity, roughness, and degree of compaction; (4) inversely with height of fall of material on free cones; (5) directly with increase of moisture up to the saturation point but inversely beyond that. A slope of repose

convex in plan view is gentler than a plane slope, which in turn is gentler than a slope concave in plan view. Irregularities completely buried beneath a pile of loose material have no influence on the angles of repose unless the buried slope continues to a free edge over which the material slumps, when increased slope of the floor decreases the slope of repose of the overlying material.

The angle of sliding friction, like the angle of repose, varies inversely with size and density of fragments and directly with their surface roughness. For the same material, however, the angle of sliding friction is definitely lower than the angle of repose.

Forces in deep excavations

The excavation of soil from a deep excavation has the following main effects:

- 1) The removal of the weight of the excavated soil results in a decrease in the vertical stress in the soil beneath the excavation.
- 2) The removal of the soil in the excavation results in a loss of lateral support around the excavation.
- 3) The excavation sides experience hydrostatic forces as the depth of the excavation goes below the depth of the water table.
- 4) Pore water pressures result in significantly large forces especially in impermeable soils.

As excavation takes place, forces are encountered on the excavation slopes due to the loss of lateral support. These forces include:

- Hydrostatic forces: Hydrostatic forces are linear in magnitude and increase as the depth of the excavation increases.

- Lateral earth pressure: This is the pressure caused to the soil itself. Lateral earth pressures in soil may be influenced by stress history, lateral movement of retaining structures and the shear strength of the soil. The smallest pressure a soil can exert is called active, the largest is called passive and the pressure when static is called at-rest. (Muthomi, 2016)

Deep excavations pose a challenge to engineers all over the world. Geotechnical failures of deep excavations have occurred and it is from these failures that more can be learned once the back analysis has been carried out. A failure is a good source of information for engineers to learn and to get more insight on the geotechnical problems to enhance knowledge. UBFC site in Kololo poses a threat to Rosco road at the risk of collapse of underlying soil mass. The neighboring built environment like drainage channels have been diverted, requiring pumping of sewage which has brought huge cost implications. Furthermore, Baskerville road has been closed due to failure of its underlying subgrade.

In order to execute a deep excavation, proper analysis should therefore be conducted. An assessment should be carried out to determine all sources of problems that may be encountered. The nature of the soil should be investigated, the level of the water table should be determined and neighbouring adjacent structure should be put into consideration before excavation starts on the construction site.

The major causes of failure in deep excavations are;

Inadequate stability analysis of an open cut excavation in North Jakarta, Indonesia, resulted in slope failure. The driven piles that had been put in place were subjected to large lateral forces that resulted in the failure of the excavation supports.

Insufficient toe penetration of steel sheet piles, would lead to excessive movement of the sheet piles toe, which might lead to kick in failure. A kick in failure results in large and sudden sagging of the ground behind the wall.

Seepage: In China, failure to support a 4.6 metre excavation resulted in the collapse of a 13 storey structure. Seepage of water into the surrounding soil and the mobilization of pore water pressures resulted in the tilting of the building and its eventual collapse.

Types of deep excavations

Depending on the challenges anticipated on the site it may be necessary to support the excavation or employ measures so as to provide solutions to these challenges.

Deep excavations are of two main types:

Open excavation: This is where there is no retaining system and the slope of the excavation slope has to be maintained at the ratio of 1:2. Open excavations are subject to ground and site conditions.

Retained Excavations: These are excavations whose sides are supported. The excavations slopes are usually vertical or near vertical. Retained excavations maximize the size of excavation and therefore suitable for urban construction. All excavations that are deeper than 3.5m may require structural support. (Muthomi, 2016)

The project scope has encountered problems such as;

- Ground deformations
- Seepage of water into excavation
- Stability of excavation slopes

Soil Type	Consideration while excavating
Sand	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Permeability for dewatering and stability of excavation bottom • Shear strength for loads on retaining structures and stability of excavation bottom
Clay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shear strength for loads on retaining structure and stability of excavation bottom • Sensitivity testing to assess the strength and stability and the possibility of reusing material as a backfill

Table 1: Key considerations for deep excavations according to soil type.

Excavation Support Systems

Excavation support systems are temporary earth retaining structures that allow the sides of excavation to be cut vertical or near vertical. They are used to minimize the excavation area, to keep the sides of deep excavations stable, and to ensure that movements will not cause damage to neighboring structures or to utilities in the surrounding ground. (Muthomi, 2016)

Excavations result in ground movements and thus the purpose of a deep excavation support system is to provide lateral support for the soil around an excavation and to limit movement of the surrounding soil system. A structural system includes wall, props, floor slabs or ground anchors. Soil-structure interaction (SSI) analysis is

important for ground supported by structures as the soil generates the loading as well as provide resistance to the load. SSI considers interaction of stiffness and deformation between structure and soil for an adequate assessment of stresses, forces and bending moments in the supporting structure.

Performance of a deep excavation is related to both stability and deformation. Deep excavations should be designed to be stable and to limit deformations to acceptable levels. A stable deep excavation is an excavation whose walls do not collapse, and whose base does not heave uncontrollably.

Stability and deformation are used to predict the performance of a deep excavation. Stability refers to resistance against failure such as basal or upheaval failure. Stability is easily evaluated with sufficient accuracy using simple limit equilibrium calculations. Deformations are the strains that occur in the surrounding soil and the movement that accompanies the strains. Finite Element Analyses is often used to evaluate deformations especially when ground movements are particularly important.

Foundations of adjacent properties and services is an important criterion in determination of the selection system.

Deep excavations in urban areas have the increased complexity of interacting with existing infrastructure. The removal of portions of a building during demolition or excavation usually results in making other parts unsafe, and it is therefore necessary to make a careful survey before commencing work to decide which portions will need securing before demolition commences. If the building adjoins other buildings it will have to be ascertained and agreed with the adjoining owners whether the walls are

party or external walls. In either case, the adjoining buildings need to be given such lateral support as is given by the building to be demolished, and it is often advisable to erect the requisite shoring before demolition proceeds too far. Care should be taken that such shoring is placed in positions that will not interfere with the erection of a new building. (Muthomi, 2016)

Every mass of soil located beneath a sloping ground surface or beneath the sloping sides of an open cut has a tendency to move upward or downward under the influence of gravity. If this tendency is encountered by the shearing resistance of the soil, the slope is stable. Otherwise a slide occurs. The material involved in the slide may consist of naturally deposited soil. Slides in natural soil may be caused by such external disturbances as under cutting the foot of an existing slope or digging an excavation with unsupported sides. On the other hand, they may also occur without external provocation on slopes that have been stable for many years.

Failure of these nature are caused by a temporary increase in porewater pressure or by a progressive deterioration of the strength of the soil. In spite of the variety of conditions that may cause a slide, almost every slide exhibits the general characteristics illustrated by Fig.2. The failure is preceded by formation of tension cracks on the upper part of the slope or beyond its crest. During the slide, the upper part of the slope or its crest. (Terzaghi, Peck and Mesri, 1996)

Figure 3: Plan of typical slide in cohesive soil. (Terzaghi, Peck and Mesri, 1996)

During the slide, the upper part of the slide known as the root, subsides, whereas the lower part known as the tongue, bulges. Hence if the original surface of the slope is a plane, the profile of the ground surface along the axis of the slide becomes distorted.

Construction operations such as cutting into slopes for highways or commercial developments, placing fills on slopes, or exposing slopes to water of a reservoir. (Terzaghi, Peck and Mesri, 1996)

Problems including slope stability include natural slopes, cuttings and excavations, sides of embankments or eth dams and many others. While dealing with natural slopes, it must be noted that landslides represent a natural hazard with important social-economical interest in all countries and this is sufficient to justify the interest in the subject. The stability of slopes may be affected by rainfall, seismic actions, natural erosion or man-made excavations. Slow downhill movements an also be produced by soil creep.

First, the contemporary geological and geotechnical nature of the problem must be considered even though the interest of a geological engineer is limited to a specific site or slope, the mechanism in slope evolution must be clearly understood. A second key element that must be introduced into analysis is represented by the hydrological conditions and their change in time. (Lancellotta, 1995)

Finally, a careful site investigation related to stratigraphical and structural features is essential. In particular, when dealing with stiff clays, an understanding of geological processes is of paramount importance and a detailed description of the material as well as any evidence of principle displacement shears induced by faults and bedding plane slips as well as minor shears of limited extent is required. (Skempton, 1966)

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is both quantitative (e.g. Quantity of ground water) and qualitative (e.g. Mechanical properties of soil) and shall draw data from both primary and secondary sources combining site investigations, laboratory testing, and data analysis to characterize recent slope failures in Kololo. I will follow a four-step approach to produce the final deliverable. In Task 1, I will identify the specific objective as stated in this research. In Task 2, I will discuss the results of the parameter being tested using literature review. In Task 3, I will use laboratory testing to more accurately characterize soil collected from different depths of interest. In Task 4, I will summarize the project's findings and presented recommendations in a slope stabilization guide to develop a suitable design to solve the problem.

This study addresses the need to provide a consistent, logical approach to slope stabilization that is founded in geotechnical research and experience, and applies to common slope failures. This project provides an example of a parametric study for future engineering research, and makes recommendations for engineers to improve the stability of slope embankments, minimize slope failure and associated damage, and decrease preventative maintenance cost with efficient stabilization methods.

3.1 Methods.

3.2 Consolidation Test using an Oedometer BS1377: Part 5:1990

In this research, I will carry out a Consolidation Test to determine the rate and magnitude of settlement in soils. The settlement values obtained by this test are due to primary consolidation only which is 90% of the total consolidation. The results of

consolidation test shall be very helpful in recommendation of the design of the solution system.

The results will be used to calculate and estimate settlement. The parameters normally required are; the compressibility of the soil, m_v and the time related parameter (coefficient of consolidation) C_v

This method covers the determination of magnitude and the rate of consolidation of a saturated or near saturated specimen of soil in the form of a disc confined laterally, subjected to vertical axial pressure and allowed to drain vertically from top to bottom surfaces, the method is mainly concerned with the primary consolidation phase but it can also be used to determine secondary consolidation characteristics. (Laboratory, 2000)

Formulae;

Initial moisture content, W_o (in %) from the specimen trimmings = $\frac{M_o - M_d}{M_d} \times 100\%$

3.3 Standard Penetration Test BS 1377: Part 9: 1990

I will carry out an insitu SPT to determine the bearing capacity of the soil. The test consists of driving a standard 50-mm outside diameter thick-walled sampler into soil at the bottom of a borehole, using repeated blows of a 63.5-kg hammer falling through 760 mm. The SPTN value is the number of blows required to achieve a penetration of 300 mm, after an initial seating drive of 150 mm.

One of the advantages of the test is that it is carried out in routine exploration boreholes of varying diameters, so that (in contrast with other in-situ tests, such as

the Cone Penetration Test) there is no need to bring special equipment to site(DE MELLO VFB, 1971)

3.4 Shearbox Test BS 1377: Part 7: 1990

During this research, I will also carry out a shearbox test to determine the soil's Shear strength, the final mechanical property of interest for the study. Shear strength refers to the level of shear stresses a material can resist without fracture. Shear strength is measured in Newtons per meter squared. Shear stresses are forces that are applied tangentially along a face of the soil. Shear strength is difficult to measure as it depends on a wide variety of factors, including the nature of the soil, the history of the particular soil sample to be measured, and the rate at which the shear forces are applied.

3.5 Undrained Triaxial Test BS 1377: Part 7: 1990

This test shall be carried out to determine the shear strength parameters of the soil sample, in terms of total stresses i.e. angle of shear resistance, cohesion and the undrained shear strength. These values will be helpful in calculating the bearing capacity of the soil and the stability of the slopes. The samples picked by systematic sampling from different depths will be subjected to constant confined pressure and to strain controlled axial loading when no change in total moisture content is allowed.

Tools: The test is carried out in Triaxial apparatus on specimens in the form of cylinders of height approximately equal to twice the diameter. Specimen's diameter range from 38 mm to 110 mm. The specimen is confined in impervious membranes between impervious end caps in a Triaxial cell which can be pressurized by water.

The axial load is increased by applying a constant rate of strain until the specimen fails normally within a period of 5 to 15 minutes.

A suitable table to record data is as shown below.

UNDRAINED TRIAXIAL TEST								
Specimen diameter = mm				Rate of stress = % per minute				
Specimen No.	Bulk Density	Moisture Content	Cell Pressure	AT FAILURE		SHEAR STRENGTH		Shear Strength at Failure C_u
				Compr. Stress	Strain	C	ϕ	

Table 2: Typical table to record Triaxial test data.

Basing on the above methods using samples obtained by systematic sampling, objectives 1 and 2 of my research shall inform objective 3 for design of a soil stabilization system. The results shall be discussed and a recommendation made based on whether the cause of the slope failure is due to the negative effect of ground water on soil's ability to resist shearing or if a modification in the methods of ensuring slope stability should be considered for example increasing the length of nails from 12 m by a certain factor informed after studying the relationship between the soil properties and the nails used for example friction. In the case of limited friction, increasing length of the nail and/or modifying the design of the nail to

increase the coefficient of friction between the soil and the nail by providing ridges should be considered after the results.

The following methodology for objective 3 therefore depends on what is causing the soil to fail. Should the results from objective 2 show that the strength of soil reduces with increase in moisture content vertically from the reference point of the surface, then my design shall be a system to lower the water table and reduce its impact on the soil quality. My proposed methodology therefore shall be designing a sub-surface drainage system.

3.6 Sub-surface drainage system

The variations in moisture content of slopes are mainly caused due to;

- Fluctuations in the movement of capillary water which is sometimes influenced by the water table.
- Seepage water from adjacent area
- Raising of ground water
- Percolation of ground water

The objective of my proposed methodology for sub surface drainage is to keep these fluctuations of moisture as minimum as possible.

Drainage is a basic way to minimize the amount of water present in the slope. Drains provide a path for water to flow away from the potential slide area and increase shear strength. Surface drains, trenches, horizontal drains, and drainage wells are some methods to control water in the slope area. Surface drains limit the amount of infiltration into slope material. Trenches, drains, and wells are used to divert water

after infiltration; their construction varies greatly by project type. Rahardjo et al. (2003) describes several drainage features designed to increase slope stability. Local conditions often govern material selection.

Typical drainage pipes used in construction vary in material, size, and installation method. Drainage pipes all have a common goal: remove water that has already infiltrated into the potential slide area. Typically surrounded with a free-draining filter media, these pipe drains help transport water from the slope. Horizontal pipe drains can be installed from the slope face, without excavation material. Installing the drains with a slight slope allows gravity to drain water from the slope material into a collection channel (Saftner and Investigator, 2017)

The system will work with a subdrain sealed under the surface receiving water along its length through perforations, porous walls or joints placed in a trench backfilled with filler material.

The subdrain will consist of trench filled with clean, granular and crushed rock material where by water is intended to pass through the interstices of the material instead of a pipe, typically referred to as a French drain.

Knowledge Gap: French drains are used in projects to solve related problems however they usually plug with fines from the adjacent ground. In this research therefore, I shall design for adequate filters such as non-woven geotextile fabric to prevent the plugging and the pipes shall be installed in such a way that the perforations face down to the bottom of the trench.

Figure 4: 3D representation of a sand drain. (Saftner and Investigator, 2017)

Groundwater has long been recognized as contributing to distress in various types of structures, and this is certainly true of slopes. A slope is more likely to fail during or after prolonged wet weather, and if the slope fails, the wet condition of the material within the slope is obvious. Several stability analysis methods are available and may be used to assess quantitatively the adverse effect of groundwater. Diverting surface water over or around a slope is helpful. In particular, any ponds that form on or near an unstable area should be breached. However, a more effective way of dealing with the problem of groundwater as a cause of instability is to extract the water from within the slope, i.e., install some form of subsurface drainage system. Groundwater naturally seeps out of all slopes to some extent, and causes failure only when the rate of discharge is inadequate, allowing excessive water pressure to build up. Subsurface drainage gives nature a helping hand by, for example, facilitating the movement of

groundwater from the rock structure in a cutting, or allowing rapid discharge from an aquifer that has an artificially obstructed outlet. (Urciuoli and Pirone, 2013)

3.7 Modification of soil Nailing

Soil nailing is a feasible technique widely used for ground reinforcement by enhancing the shear resistance of soil and the skin friction at the interface between the grout and soil mass .Although most grouting practice has been performed by gravitationally filling the voids of soil formation without pressurization, recently a number of pressurized grouting applications have been successfully carried out. Pressurized grouting has been frequently adopted in a soil-nailing system that is widely used to improve slope stability. Compared with adopting gravitational grouting, the soil-nailing system using pressurized grouting has many advantages: (1) increase in groutability to completely backfill the borehole; (2) expansion of grouting area; (3) increase in shear strength at the interface between the grout and soil mass; and (4) economic efficiency. Soil nailing using pressurized grouting has been empirically performed in most reinforcement applications without theoretical validation because the interaction between the pressurized grout and adjacent soil mass is so complicated that there have been few attempts to investigate relevant models. (Seo *et al.*, 2012)

Based on my scope conditions, soil nailing has failed to stabilize the slope. I therefore recommend modifications made on the design of the soil nail. Since the soil mass parameters cannot be altered, this research shall focus on the nail quality to increase friction between the nail and the soil mass.

The pullout frictional coefficient (f^*) at the interface between soil and reinforcement is discussed in this section.

Figure 5: Forces during soil geo nailing.

Schematic of stress distribution exerted around the reinforcement in the pullout test setup. In this stress configuration, the pullout frictional coefficient can be derived as follows.

$$f^* = \frac{F}{2bL\sigma_m}$$

Where F = pullout force; b = width of planar strip; L = embedded length in soil; and σ_m = average normal stress acting on the interface of reinforcement.

Increasing the value of the average normal stress would increase the interface of reinforcement and reduce the probability of failure.

Recommendations:

1. The nail should be designed with ridges to increase the coefficient of friction at the interface of reinforcement.
2. The length of the 12m nail used should be increased by a factor that will in turn friction beyond maximum friction required to prevent method failure.

4.0 DATA ANALYSIS, PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.1 Area of study

The area of study is located at plot 1, Baskerville Avenue, Kampala District. Some neighbors of the site are the Burundi Embassy, and City High school. This area was selected because it is an ongoing which provides access to soil samples for study very deep below the subsoil, also the area is well positioned in the area of Kololo that has registered several slope stability challenges. This makes the research ideal for reference to other sites within the same geographical scope.

4.2 Sources of Information

This study used both primary and secondary data sources to realize objectives 1 and 2. These included; reports and laboratory test data on samples obtained from the site. Further information about the site was provided orally through interactions with the site management personnel and client at Infrastructure Projects Limited and Private Sector foundation Uganda.

4.3 Sampling Technique

Samples were picked by systematic sampling along the stratigraphy in a horizontal orientation. This is done to establish differences in soil conditions with respect to location of the water table. Different tools were used including cores, a hammer, chisel and packaging gear (polythene bags)

4.4 Variables definitions and measurements

The study has both an independent and a dependent variable. The dependent variable is “Slope stability” which is being tested and measured in the laboratory tests and model experiments conducted. Slope stability is the degree to which a soil mass or

slope will withstand a given force/load. Slope stability will be measured using data obtained the shear box test but also data about effective stress as analyzed from secondary data.

The independent variable is the Impact of water table because it is the one being controlled or changed basing on the location of the water table along different layers of the stratigraphy. Different soil samples obtained from different depths chosen systematically will show the impact at different regions within the multi-layered soil mass.

4.5 Procedure for data collection (undrained Tri axial test)

Samples from the field trial points were well protected against moisture loss using polythene bags that were tied on the top and were taken to the laboratory for testing. During sample collection, several tools were used including; hammer, metallic cores, Handy GPS, polythene bags and Personal Protective Equipment.

Systematic sampling was used to obtain soil samples in a horizontal orientation from a failed slope which was subject to geo nailing. Systematic sampling was done at different depths to study the strength characteristics of all three samples along the stratigraphy of varying moisture content due to influence of the water table. A handy GPS was used to obtain the geographical location of the trial points. The cores were driven into the soil mass using a hammer

The procedure for sample preparation was carried on according to **BS 1377: Part 7: 1990** as follows;

- a) The sample was removed from the core to ascertain the condition of the soil. This was done using a chisel and into the mould.
- b) The sample was then pushed into a different mould of relatively bigger diameter using a specific piece of wood, from which it would be measured as shown in Appendix 1.
- c) The specimen is then placed on the base end cap and the top cap is placed on the specimen. Filter stones were then put at the top and bottom of the specimen.
- d) The membrane was fitted to the stretcher and was placed around the specimen. The membrane was then sealed to end caps by means of rubber O-rings without entrapping air.
- e) The specimen was then placed centrally on the base pedestal of the triaxial cell ensuring that it is in the correct vertical alignment.
- f) The triaxial cell was filled with water and pressurized. Final adjustments were made and logging was then started which ran for some time.
- g) The machine was then stopped and the cell emptied.

The test was carried out in a triaxial apparatus on specimen in the form of cylinders of height approximately equal to twice the diameter. The diameter of specimens was 38mm. The specimens are shown in Appendix 1.

During the test, the specimen was confined in an impervious membrane between impervious end caps in a triaxial cell which was pressurized by water. The axial load was increased by applying a constant rate of strain until the specimen failed. This happened within a period of 5-15 minutes.

4.6 Data Collection Instruments

This research used both laboratory and field equipment to collect data but also use computer aided software to analyze secondary data provided within the Geotechnical report obtained. Sampling was carried out using soil cores of diameter 100mm which were driven horizontally into the soil mass using a hand hammer and were transported to the laboratory in polythene bags to avoid moisture loss. A handy GPS was used to locate specific trial points of sample extraction. The triaxial test was carried out in a tri-axial apparatus on specimens in the form of cylinders of height approximately equal to twice the diameter. The following tools were used; Triaxial cell, trimming knife, chisel, oven and moulds.

4.7 Quality Control

The reliability and validity of techniques and instruments used for research are regulated by Engineering standards especially British standards. The data was gathered using instruments and tools physically but also use of photographic camera to obtain photographs for study and analysis. The use of tank for research design is representative of the ideal soil stratigraphy situation to understand how seepage in the artesian conditions occurs. The seepage model is based on the assumptions that due to increased rainfalls received, and lack of surface protection gear to prevent infiltration, the accumulation of water caused artesian seepage in the soil mass contributing to increased slope failure in the later stages of construction.

The tank is transparent which allows for proper monitoring of the soil condition as would be in the soil on site.

4.8 Data Collection and Analysis

The data obtained was analyzed using statistical data analysis aided by computer software like Microsoft Excel, this was used because processed data was provided through the geotechnical report and graphs generated to compare different parameters.

The research questions set were answered as follows;

Research Question 1: What mechanical properties of the soil affect soil stability?

The study found out that consolidation, bearing capacity and shear strength all affect soil stability. It however should be noted that other factors that are not mentioned in the study could as well affect soil stability. The study proved that the consolidation test results show a variation in soil classification of different strata. The soils can be classified as low permeability soils (clays) whose consolidation takes place slowly and continuously over a long period of time-months, years or even decades after construction.

The Tri-axial test showed that Shear strength of the soil reduces with increase in soil depth as one moves deeper the stratigraphy of the soil while the Standard Penetration test conducted and reviewed through secondary data proved that when moisture content is high around water table region, the allowable bearing capacity is lower at the same depth as compared to bearing capacities of soils obtained from regions that exist above the ground water level.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between soil strength and Ground water quantity?

From the data analyzed, the study found out that high volumes of ground water quantity have a negative effect on soil stability. The higher the quantities, the lower the factor of safety, and in turn, the lower the soil stability.

Research Question 3: What suitable slope stabilization mechanism can be applied?

The study recommends a subsurface drainage system based on the site conditions characterized by lack of enough space that would be required for other mechanisms, this research however proposes that soil mass should have been covered from further infiltration of water that worsened the situation, using water proof membrane.

4.9 Ethical Considerations

This research was conducted on a government facility and therefore issues of methodology used and access to the site were regulated by Government of Uganda through its representative body of Private Sector Foundation Uganda. The review and any use of all secondary data were subject to approval by Government for specifically academic purpose. A level of confidentiality was maintained during and after this study with regards to certain sections of project works.

A copy of this document was provided to the Government of Uganda through its responsible office to check with consistencies as agreed in verbal oath taken before the research.

4.10 Methodological constraints

During the study, methods applied had several limits and weaknesses which I believe hindered the findings and these include;

- The source of secondary data available (Geotechnical report) contained analyzed data from the tests carried out. This made interpretation of varying parameters different since raw data wasn't captured in the report attached as Annex 1.
- Sample collection for the undrained triaxial test was made difficult due to the risk of the failed slope. The process was risky and posed as a hinderance to the study.

4.11 Data Analysis, Presentation and Interpretation of Findings

As stated under Limitations of the study in Chapter 1, challenges with sample collection meant that secondary data was to be used to analyze soil conditions. The following tests were therefore analyzed using secondary data.

- Consolidation Test
- Standard Penetration Test

An Undrained Triaxial test was conducted in the lab to realize the relationship between soil stability and quantity of water table using values of moisture content and shear strength of different samples systematically picked along the soil stratigraphy in a horizontal orientation.

According to Nammuli Veronica 2016, several tests were carried out to determine the geotechnical information including design parameters for the proposed structural foundations and any associated infrastructure. These facts are presented in Geotechnical Investigations Service Final Report Ref:2016/137 prepared by TECLAB Limited for SSENTONGO & PARTNERS.

The data and results discussed here is therefore from the above report whose access for reference and use in my research has been granted by the client (Private sector Foundation Uganda)

4.12 Borehole Drilling

The field exploratory activities were conducted in accordance with BS 5930:1999 “Code of Practice for Site Investigations” and included drilling of two (02) boreholes to a maximum depth of 20m conducting standard penetration tests (SPT) at 1.5m intervals, logging and sampling from each borehole for laboratory testing.

The boreholes were drilled using the percussion drilling method with the Dando-2000 as the drilling rig. The diameter of the exploratory hole was 130mm. Disturbed samples were taken at each core run to enable accurate profiling of the strata. A summary of the field activities carried out and the location of the exploratory holes is given in table below. All coordinates are given in UTM 36N WGS84.

BH No.	Start Date	Date Completed	Drilling Depth (m)	No. of Disturbed Samples	No. of Undisturbed Samples	No. of SPTs	Coordinates	Elevation (m)
BH 1	9/9/2016	10/9/2016	20	13	1	13	E 0455536, N 0036637	1188
BH 2	11/9/2016	12/9/2016	20	13	1	13	E 0455547, N 0036662	1176

Table 3: Raw data on samples picked according to secondary data.

According to the Geotechnical report, strength tests were carried out on undisturbed samples and included direct shear box test and consolidation test.

Consolidation Test using an Oedometer BS1377: Part 5:1990

This was achieved using statistical data analysis of secondary data using Microsoft Excel.

In this research, a Consolidation test was required to determine the rate and magnitude of settlement in soils. The settlement values obtained by this test are due to primary consolidation only which is 90% of the total consolidation. The results of consolidation test shall be very helpful in recommendation of the design of the solution system.

The results will be used to calculate and estimate settlement. The parameters normally required are; the compressibility of the soil, m_v and the time related parameter (coefficient of consolidation) C_v

This method covers the determination of magnitude and the rate of consolidation of a saturated or near saturated specimen of soil in the form of a disc confined laterally, subjected to vertical axial pressure and allowed to drain vertically from top to bottom surfaces, the method is mainly concerned with the primary consolidation phase but it can also be used to determine secondary consolidation characteristics. (Laboratory, 2000)

According to Nammuli Veronica 2016, the summary of the consolidation test parameters is presented as shown below.

SUMMARY OF CONSOLIDATION TEST RESULTS

Sample Source	Depth (m)	Pre-consolidation pressure (kN/m ²)	Overburden Pressure (kN/m ²)	Compression Index, C _c	Coefficient of Volume Compressibility M _v (m ² /MN)			Coefficient of Consolidation C _v (m ² /yr)			Permeability, k (m/s) x10 ⁻⁹		
					Min	Max	Ave	Min	Max	Ave	Min	Max	Ave
BH1	5.5-6.0	120	101.2	0.033	0.054	5.482	1.091	9.338	17.99	12.937	1.8469E-09	3.06803E-07	5.82004E-08
BH2	12.5-13.0	150	239.1	0.052	0.078	1.538	0.501	10.785	18.57	14.696	4.35964E-09	5.20109E-08	2.06214E-08

Table 4: Consolidation test results (Plot 1 Baskerville Avenue Geotechnical Report, 2016)

The analysis was based on the typical values for compression index, coefficient of compressibility and coefficient of consolidation given in Tables 5, 6 & 7 respectively.

Compression Index	Compressibility Behavior	Clay Type
>0.3	Very High	Soft Clay
0.3-0.15	High	Clay
0.15-0.075	Medium	Silt
<0.075	Low	Sandy Clay

Table 5: Typical Values of Compression Index for different fine-grained soils (Cc)

The compression index C_c is one of the best-known parameters in soil mechanics. It is useful both in developing theoretical concepts and in carrying out practical calculations (Wesley, 1988)

C_c is related to the compressibility of the soil although the relationship is not a direct one. A large number of publications are now available to warrant a closer look at the validity, accuracy, and usefulness of many available empirical formulas for C_c estimation of fine-grained soils to their liquid limit (LL). Among the more widely used equations for estimating C_c are those developed by Skempton (1944), Terzaghi and Peck (1948), and Hough (1957). Other less well-known equations include Tsuchida (1991), Azzouz et al. (1976), Koppula (1981). (Al-khafaji *et al.*, 2015)

According to Terzaghi and Peck (1948), the equation for C_c is given by $C_c = 0.009(LL - 10)$ as shown in the graph. The graph shows the comparison of compression indices predicted on the basis of the equation.

The test data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel to study the coefficient of compressibility (C_c). It should be understood that when structures are built on

saturated soils, the load is presumed to be carried initially by incompressible water within the soil voids.

Figure 6: A graph of Cc variations along the depth.

From the graph, the trends show how both soil samples behave after varying the compression index along the depth of the stratigraphy.

BH 1

Samples picked from BH 1 show a constant compression index between 1-6.0m of just above 0.2 which also shows that they possess a high compressibility behavior and therefore can be classified as clay soils according to Lambe and William.

There's a registered dip in the compression index at 7.0m signaling the presence of silt with a medium compressibility behavior.

The trend thereafter peaks around 10m, attributed to the influence of the water table around the depth of the stratigraphy. The trend thereafter falls gradually indicating a fall in compression index Cc.

BH 2

Sample obtained at a depth of 1m from the surface exhibit a compression index of just above 0.2, which according to Lambe and William 1979, indicates a high compressibility behavior characteristic of clay soils.

As the depth increases, the compression increases to about 0.5. This figure is greater than 0.3 which according to Lambe and William describes a very high compressibility behavior and presence of clay. According to this research, this is attributed to the influence of water table on the soil. The trend thereafter falls around 13.5m and then rises again due to variations in the soil conditions.

Figure 7: A graph of Cc against LL

From the above graph, it can be argued therefore that soils with high values of Cc (or of LL) naturally have high compressibility. In this case, the relationship can be explained by the compression index equation for undisturbed samples used.

Since the Liquid Limit is the measure of the water attracted to these clay soils, a correlation between Liquid Limit and soil compression index would be expected. It is however important to note that estimations of compression index are dependent on other factors including in situ moisture content and voids ratio. According to Herrero (1983) the relationship between C_c and moisture content is given by the formula

$$C_c = 0.01(w - 7.549)$$

The relationship between Moisture content and compressive index is directly proportional. The higher the moisture content, the higher the compressive index and a proportional high compressive behavior.

However, it is important to remember that the focus of this study is with respect to the effect of the water table and both samples clearly show that compressive samples extracted from the depth within 9.50-10.5 (which is the water depth according to the stratigraphy), are highest and are greater than 0.3 which identifies the soils as soft clays with very high compressive behavior.

Coefficient m_v (m^2/MN)	Compressibility	Typical Material
<0.05	Very Low	Heavily over consolidated clays and weathered rock
0.05-0.1	Low	Till (Boulder Clay)
0.1-0.3	Medium	Fluvio-glacial and lacustrine clay
0.3-1.5	High	Normally-consolidated alluvial clay
>1.5	Very High	Organic alluvial clay

Table 6: Typical Values for the coefficient of volume compressibility m_v after Head (1982)

The coefficient (m_v) is defined as the compression of a soil layer, per unit of original thickness per unit increase of effective stress in the load range exceeding pre consolidation stress. (Modified after Terzaghi and Peck, 1948, p. 64.)

C_v (m^2/yr)	Rate of consolidation	Typical material
<0.01	Very low	
0.1-1.0	Low	>25% clay
1-10	Medium	15-25% clay
10-100	High	<15% silt
>100	Very high	

Table 7: Values for the coefficient of consolidation (C_v) after Lambe & William (1979)

BH 1 (5.5-6.0m)

The pre-consolidation pressure at 5.5-6.0m was 120 kN/m^2 and the overburden pressure was 101.2 kN/m^2 . Based on the maximum coefficient of consolidation obtained ($12.94 \text{ m}^2/\text{yr}$), the rate of consolidation for the sample obtained was high, (Lambe and Whitman, 1979) (This shows that the sample contained less than 15% silt. The compression index was less than 0.3, indicating that the soils are mostly clay.

BH 2 (12.5-13.0)

The pre-consolidation pressure at 12.5-6.0m was 150 kN/m^2 and the overburden pressure was 239.1 kN/m^2 . Based on the maximum coefficient of consolidation obtained ($14.696 \text{ m}^2/\text{yr}$), the rate of consolidation was high (Lambe and Whitman, 1979) This shows that the sample contained less than 15% silt. The compression index was less than 0.3 which showed that the soils are mostly silty clays.

4.14 Conclusion;

The consolidation test results show the variation in soil classification of different strata. The soils can be classified as low permeability soils (clays) whose consolidation takes place slowly and continuously over a long period of time- months, years or even decades after construction. On the contrary, if this research had a control experiment of studying high permeability soils (coarse grained soils), this process would take relatively short time for completion, with the result that almost all of the settlement occurring during the construction period.

The details of consolidation test results are presented as **Appendix 2**.

4.15 Undrained Triaxial Test BS 1377: Part 7: 1990

As stated in my proposed methodology, I carried out an undrained Triaxial test from Teclab Engineers Laboratory after securing permission to use the site by the client (Private Sector Foundation)

Details of the sample collection are shown in the table below.

TP No.	Date	Core Diameter Size (mm)	Depth (m)	No. of undisturbed samples	No. of disturbed samples	Coordinates
TP 1	6/01/2020	100	5.5	1	0	E0455602 N0036341
TP 2	6/01/2020	100	9.5	1	0	E0455633 N0036347
TP 3	6/01/2020	100	1.3	1	0	E0455572 N0036324

Table 8: Sample collection data

The stress strain relation was computed and is shown by the stress strain curves below.

Project location	Plot No.1, Baskerville Avenue		
Project reference		Sample depth (m)	5.50
Borehole number	TP1	Sample type	Undisturbed
Sample number		Specimen orientation	Horizontal

Figure 8: Stress strain curves for TP 1

Project location	Plot No.1, Baskerville Avenue		
Project reference		Sample depth (m)	9.50
Borehole number	TP2	Sample type	Undisturbed
Sample number		Specimen orientation	Horizontal

Figure 9: Stress strain curves for TP 2

Figure 10: Stress strain curves for TP 3.

The graphs above show three specimens for each Trial Point which were considered to reduce the error margin that could have been realized due to coring errors or during sample preparation in the laboratory.

Each graph shows the stress-strain behavior for each confining pressure. The curves show deviator stress which is defined as $\delta_1 - \delta_3$ where δ_1 and δ_3 are the normal stresses in the axial and radial directions, against the axial strain in percentage.

Stress is the force per unit area of the specimens while the strain is the extension per unit length of the specimen.

It is observed that deviatoric stress increases with the increase in confining pressure. It is also noted that deviatoric stress attains its peak state at a small strain level for extremely low confining pressures while the deviatoric stress peaked at a moderate strain level for low to high confining pressures.

Details of the triaxial test are showed in **Appendix 6**

4.16 Checking Slope stability (Shearbox Test)

The analysis of slopes is important because of the dangers to both structures and life that can be caused by two types of problem;

- a) Where construction or excavation causes stress changes in the soil which lead to failure in previously stable ground.
- b) Where construction or excavation reactivates movement of preexisting shear surface in the soil, usually part of an ancient and pre-existing landslide. (Blake, 1996)

This study analyzed secondary data obtained from carrying out shearbox test as recorded in the geotechnical report.

The test was carried out in accordance with BS 1377: Part 7 1990. The summary of shear strength parameters are as shown below in the Table. Details of the shear strength test results are as shown in the Annex report attached. The bulk densities of the samples tested from BH 1 and BH 2 were 1833 kg/m³ and 1783 kg/m³ respectively. These were tested under typical of saturated ground conditions. The unmodified angles of internal friction were 29.3° and 5.0° respectively for BH 1 and BH 2. The unmodified cohesion values were 56.2 Kpa and 13.9 Kpa.

Borehole No.	Depth (m)	Bulk Density (Kg/m ³)	Cohesion (KPa)	Angle of Internal Friction (Φ)
BH 1	5.5-6.0	1.833	56.2	29.3
BH 2	12.5-13.0	1.783	13.9	5.0

Table 9: Shearbox test data and result (Namuli, 2016)

Before failure, the slope was cut into a natural ground of an original soil mass. With the given strength parameters shown above, the drained slope stability

analysis indicated stable slopes under reasonable ground-water (GW) levels expected in the cut slope. However, after a period of unusually intense rainfall, the slope suffered a shallow slip to about 1m to 1.5m depth with a vertical scarp near the top of the cut slope.

4.17 Possible causes of failure

The large overburden stress relief resulting from the large hill cut to form the embankment slope produced soils at high pore-water suction rate. This resulted into higher factors of safety after cutting. These factors of safety would increase immediately after cutting. These factors of safety would decrease with time since effective stresses decrease from pore-water increases, as soon as soils are exposed to groundwater rise from rainfall infiltration. The water table that was at 10m was now brought closer to the ground surface from the removal of overburden soils.

4.18 Standard Penetration Test BS 1377: Part 9: 1990

In-situ Standard Penetration Testing (SPT) was carried out within the borehole at 1.5m intervals. SPT was carried out using a 63.5 kg driving hammer falling ‘freely’ from a height of 760mm. The number of blows required to drive the sampler each 150mm increment of a total of 450mm penetration was recorded. The total blow count for the first 150mm was discarded due to possible presence of loose materials or cuttings from the drilling operation. The sum of the blow counts for the last two (2) increments (i.e. last 300mm) were considered to be the measured uncorrected SPT N-value. **Tables 11 & 12** below summarize the Standard Penetration Test (SPT) results for the boreholes. Drilling logs and core pictorial logs are also shown in the Annex report.

SPT Correction

The measured SPT 'N' values were corrected for the overburden, equipment and borehole diameter to establish the corrected SPT ' N_{cor} ' values, from which estimated soil design parameters and soil consistency were ascertained. The overburden correction factor for clayey soil was taken to be 1.0. The equipment and borehole size correction factors used are in **Table 10**.

- An equipment and borehole size correction factors apply.
- The effect of overburden is negligible for cohesive soils, and no overburden correction factor C_N is required.
- The energy ratio is normalized to 60% of total energy, N_{60} .
- Corrected SPT 'N' value, $N_{cor} = N_{60} = C_N C_{ER} N$. Where, N is measured SPT 'N' value and C_{ER} is equipment & borehole correction factor given by;

$$C_{ER} = C_H C_R C_S C_B$$

4.19 Bearing Capacity Determination

The corrected SPT 'N' values (N_{cor}) in **Tables 11 & 12** were averaged for the entire depth investigated. From the borehole logs and classification spoil test results, the borehole soils are generally silts in nature, with sands and a few clays. The empirical relationship established by Peck et al., (1974) between corrected SPT 'N' values (N_{cor}) and unconfined compressive strength (Q_u) was used and is given below.

$$Q_u = kN_{cor} \text{ (kPa)}$$

Where, k is the proportionality factor established from empirical correlations between the unconfined compressive strength (Q_u) and the corrected SPT 'N' values (N_{cor})

Table 7: Energy Ratio correction factors to be applied to SPT value to account for equipment and borehole size (Skempton, 1986 and Takimatsu and Seed, 1987)

To account for Parameter	Correction Factor
Hammer - Release - Country	
Hammer (C_H)	
Donut - free fall (Tombi) - Japan	1.3
Donut - rope and pulley - Japan	1.1
Safety - rope and pulley - USA	1.0
Donut - free fall (Trip) - Europe	1.0
Donut - rope and pulley - China	0.5
Donut - rope and pulley - USA	0.75
Rod length (C_R)	
>10m	1.0
10m to 6m	0.95
6m to 4m	0.85
4m to 3m	0.75
Sampler (C_s)	
Standard	1.0
US Sampler without liners	1.2
Borehole 65mm - 115mm	1.0
Diameter (C_B) 150mm	1.05
200mm	1.15

Table 10: SPT Correction values for different standards (Namuli, 2016)

A value of $k = 12$ has been recommended by Bowles (1996) for a standard energy ratio, $R_{es} = 70\%$. However, based on the 60% standard energy ratio adopted in United Kingdom, a value of $k = 13.27$ has been recommended and was used in the computation of the unconfined compressive strength. Thereafter the undrained cohesion (c_u) was obtained from the unconfined compressive strength (q_u) as,

$$c_u = \frac{q_u}{2} \text{ kPa}$$

The ultimate bearing capacity (q_{ult}) was computed from the relationship,

$$q_{ult} = c_u N_c \text{ kPa}$$

Where, N_c is the bearing capacity factor for clay/silt soils

Skempton (1951) gives different bearing capacity factor N_c for clay soils with respect to depth and foundation with ratio for different shapes of foundations. For purposes of computations, the least bearing capacity factor N_c of 5.14 was used.

The approximate allowable bearing capacity (q_{all}) was obtained by dividing the ultimate bearing capacity (q_{ult}) by the Factor of Safety (FoS) of 3.0 irrespective of the site conditions.

For comparison purposes, Clayton (1993) stated that it is better to always make a rapid, albeit crude estimate of the allowable bearing capacities using more than one method. In this research, a quick approximation of the allowable bearing capacities is given by the Terzaghi and Peck (1948) relationship below.

$q_a = 10N$ Where q_a is in kPa

The allowable bearing capacities from the two methods were almost identical as shown in the Tables 3 & 4. Detailed results for bearing capacities are shown in Appendix 3.

BH No.	Depth (m)	Predominant Soil Fraction	Measured SPT 'N' Value N	Corrected SPT 'N' Value N_{COR}	Allowable Bearing Capacity By Terzaghi and Peck (1948)	Allowable Bearing Capacity Terzaghi and Peck, (1967)
BH01	1.50	Clayey Silts	10	<u>8</u>	75	84
	3.00		10	<u>8</u>	75	84
	4.50		12	<u>10</u>	102	114
	6.00		17	<u>14</u>	145	161
	7.50	Silty Clay	>60	<u>>60</u>	>600	>600
	9.00	Clayey Silts	15	<u>14</u>	143	159
	10.50	Sandy Silts	9	<u>8</u>	82	92
	12.00		39	<u>34</u>	340	378
	13.5		38	<u>32</u>	317	500
	15.0		>60	<u>>60</u>	>600	>600
	16.5	Silty Sands	>60	<u>>60</u>	>600	>600
	18.0		47	<u>31</u>	390	390
	19.5		47	<u>31</u>	390	390

Table 11: Bearing Capacity based on SPT-N Values

BH No.	Depth (m)	Predominant Soil Fraction	Measured SPT 'N' Value N	Corrected SPT 'N' Value N_{COR}	Allowable Bearing Capacity By Terzaghi and Peck (1948)	Allowable Bearing Capacity By Terzaghi and Peck, (1967)
BH02	1.50	Clayey Silts	8	<u>6</u>	60	67
	3.00		8	<u>6</u>	60	67
	4.50		27	<u>23</u>	230	256
	6.00		30	<u>23</u>	255	210
	7.50	Silty Clay	28	<u>27</u>	266	296
	9.00	Clayey Silts	31	<u>29</u>	295	328
	10.50	Sandy Silts	10	<u>9</u>	92	102
	12.00		18	<u>16</u>	158	175
	13.5		41	<u>28</u>	350	350
	15.0		25	<u>20</u>	202	225
	16.5	Silty Sands	36	<u>28</u>	282	314
	18.0		46	<u>35</u>	351	391
	19.5		52	<u>39</u>	387	431

Table 12: Bearing Capacity based on SPT-N Values

The SPT data is explained by the graph below.

Figure 11: A graph showing Q_{all} variations along the depth.

The above graph shows the changes in allowable bearing capacity along the depth of the stratigraphy of the soil mass.

BH 1

Soil sample picked from BH 1 exhibited initial bearing capacity below 100 N close to the reference point (surface) due to its interaction with surface vibrations and disturbances from earth moving equipment during construction and site clearance, this sample was near the reference point (surface). The soils are clayey silts. The bearing capacity then increases but later drops due to the influence of water table around 10.5m.

BH2

Samples obtained from this borehole show similar characteristics with a gradual increase in bearing capacity as depth increases. The sample also exhibits a fall in the bearing capacity around the water table depth which further explains the effect of ground water on bearing capacity which is further explained by the graph below.

Figure 12: Moisture content variation along the depth.

From the figure above moisture content behaves in the same way just like allowable bearing capacity along the stratigraphy. This shows the relationship between bearing capacities of different soil strata and moisture content.

The high the moisture content, the high the probability of a soil sample to have a low bearing capacity. However, this research acknowledges that moisture content is not a sufficient determinant of bearing capacity and therefore suggests a study of particle structure of each soil sample since the soils are non-homogeneous.

Conclusion: From the two graphs shown above, it can be seen that when moisture content is high, the allowable bearing capacity is low at the same depth.

The water table has an effect on the bearing capacity of the soil. According to Terzaghi, if the water table is at a depth of not less than the breadth B of the foundation, the expression for net ultimate bearing capacity for a strip footing is given by;

$$Q_{u\ net} = cN_c + \gamma z(N_q - 1) + 0.5\gamma B N_\gamma$$

The safe bearing capacity is therefore the above expression divided by the factor

of safety plus element $\gamma z \frac{cN_c + \gamma z(N_q - 1) + 0.5\gamma B N_\gamma}{F} + \gamma z$

F

When the water table rises to a depth of less than B below the foundation, the equation becomes $Q_{u\ net} = cN_c + \gamma z(N_q - 1) + 0.5\gamma B N_\gamma$

However, in the case of the scope of this study, the water table is above the foundation at a depth of 10.5m and for this case, Terzaghi's expression are in the form $Q_{u\ net} = cN_c + \sigma'_v (N_q - 1) + 0.5\gamma B N_\gamma$

Where σ'_v = effective overburden pressure removed. From the equation, it can be seen, from these circumstances that the bearing capacity is affected by ground water.

Details of SPT are attached as **Appendix 3**.

4.20 Project Design

The design for the project recognizes several external parameters which influence the system in place and these include;

- The effect of rainfall to the exposed cut slope increased the amount of water in the soil and contributed to the deterioration of the stability by further reducing the factor of safety. This flow shall be modelled for within the prototype.
- The influence of vertical forces exerted by traffic using the Roscoe road. Since the site is closer to the road, the loads are transmitted to the soil mass. Necessary assumptions will be taken into considering in the model.
- The influence of horizontal forces from the constructed structure. The superstructure exerts loads to the cut slope of the soil mass and this too shall be catered for in the following model.

4.21 FLOW MODEL

Assumptions for flow in layered media.

- Flow in layered media involves investigation of groundwater flow through a class of aquifer formations with an isotropic permeability.
- This study takes an assumption that all flow before excavation works was consistent with artesian conditions i.e. flow is upwards since water moves from regions of high concentration to regions of low concentration.
- The flow of water during underground water drainage is horizontal due to pressure differences at the soil-air interface.
- The study also takes the layers of the soil to be horizontal.

- The aquifers are composed of a number of layers of rocks with different permeabilities. The study also assumes that layers of rocks are horizontal.

Consider the horizontal flow through a stratified layer with N layers with hydraulic conductivity K_1, K_2, \dots, K_N and thickness b_1, b_2, \dots, b_N

Then for each layer, Darcy's law gives; $q_i = -b_i K_i \frac{(h_1 - h_2)}{L} \dots \dots \dots$ (i)

Since the distance through the aquifer must be equal, the sum of the discharges through each layer, which is the total discharge is given by;

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^N q_i \dots \dots \dots (ii)$$

Using total discharge and effective horizontal hydraulic conductivity K_h , Darcy's law gives; $Q = -b K_h \frac{(h_1 - h_2)}{L} \dots \dots \dots$ (iii)

Substituting for Q_i in (ii) and eliminating Q from equations (i) and (iii) gives;

$$-b K_h \frac{(h_1 - h_2)}{L} = - \sum_{i=1}^N b_i K_i \left(\frac{h_1 - h_2}{L} \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow K_h = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N b_i K_i}{b}$$

Which is the weighted arithmetic mean of the hydraulic conductivities in terms of transmissivity (Effective hydraulic conductivity at right angles to the layers)

In the vertical flow across the layers of the aquifers, let Δh_i be the head drop across the i^{th} layer, since mass continuity demands that, the discharge across each layer must be the same, using Darcy's law, we have;

$$Q = K_i \frac{\Delta h_i}{b_i} \text{ for } i = 1, 2, \dots, N \dots \dots (1)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \Delta h_i = h_1 - h_2 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Using the effective hydraulic vertical conductivity K_v in Darcy's law gives;

$$Q = K_v \frac{(h_1 - h_2)}{b} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

From equations (1) and (2), we have;

$$h_1 - h_2 = - \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{Q b_i}{K_i}$$

Substituting for $h_1 - h_2$ in (3) and re-arranging gives;

$$K_v = \frac{b}{\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{b_i}{k_i}}$$

-This is the weighted harmonic mean of the hydraulic conductivities.

From consideration two, the influence of vertical loads imposed by traffic along Roscoe road. This is analyzed in terms of effective stress imposed on the slope. Effective stress, σ' is the normal stress to which soil particles are subjected. It is actually the portion of the stress which is carried by the soil grains themselves (i.e. particle to particle contact) Effective stress is either due to the load that is placed on the soil particles or the self-weight of the particles themselves.

σ' = Effective stress i.e. the amount of stress that the particles feel

u = Pore pressure (pressure acting on the soil particles from the water in the pore spaces)

Due to the presence of water in the soil mass, the effective vertical stress is less due to buoyancy.

4.22 Artesian Flow model prototype.

Tools used: Transparent tank, pipe sections, elbows, male connectors, thread tape, soil, pressurized water tap, wooden stand, water tube.

Procedure.

- a) A transparent tank was obtained and fitted with 3 piezometers at different heights i.e. 5, 10 and 15 inches representing the site conditions at 3.3m, 5.5m and 9.5m respectively synonymous with the Trial points for sample collection for the Tri axial test conducted.
- b) The tank was fitted with an inflow pipe below it with a gate valve to control the amount of water inflow but also prevent backflow during artesian condition.
- c) The tank was then filled with soil picked from the site at the different heights of 3.3m, 5.5m and 9.5m.
- d) Water was then connected to the inlet pipe through an adjustable tube to contain pressure and the upward seepage of water was monitored in terms of time taken to seep through each layer.

NOTE: Each piezometer was fitted at the boundary of different soil types used in the experiment.

4.23 Observation

Upward seepage through the tank was observed from the bottom emptying into the upper space left for reserve overflow. To ensure constant head, water was let to overflow from the tank.

The height of water in piezometer I is the true representation of the pore pressure at 15 inches or 9.5m in the site, the height of water in piezometer II is the true representation of the pore pressure at 10 inches or 5.5m in the site while the height of water in piezometer III is the true representation of pore pressure at 5 inches or 3.3m in the site. The collected data can be shown below;

Piezometer	Height of piezometers (inches)	Representative Site depth (m)	Time to seep through layer (s)	Height of water (inches)
I	15	9.5	120	13
II	10	5.5	300	9.4
III	5	3.3	567	4

Table 13: Raw data collected during the experiment

From the experiment, the upward seepage force per unit volume of soil would be calculated.

Figure 13: Prototype design for upward seepage study.

Figure 14: The model setup for seepage flow experiment

Figure 15: 2D image of the seepage tank (Rahardjo et al., 2010)

The height of water H_1 is 5 inches = 0.127m

The height of granular soil H_2 is 13 inches = 0.3302m

The value of $h = 6$ inches = 0.1524m

$Z = 5$ inches = 0.127m

The saturated unit weight according to secondary data $\gamma_{sat} = 18.6$ kN/M³

The hydraulic conductivity of the soil is $k = 0.13$ cm/sec.

The area of the tank (cylindrical in this case) $A = 2\pi rh + 2\pi r^2$

$$A = (2 * \pi * 0.1334 * 0.4572) + (2 * \pi * 0.1334^2)$$

$$A = 0.495m^2$$

4.24 Calculation:

Consider the unit weight of water as $\gamma_w = 9.81$ kN/m³

The hydraulic gradient i is given by $i = \frac{h}{H_2} = \frac{0.1524}{0.3302} = 0.462$

Find the rate of upward seepage of water (q) using the equation $q = kiA$

$$q = (0.0013 * 0.462 * 0.495)$$

$$q = 2.973 \times 10^{-4} m^3/s$$

4.25 Stresses:

Point A (5 inches): $\sigma_A = H_1\gamma_w = 0.127 \times 9.81 = 1.25$ kN/m²

$$u_A = H_1\gamma_w = 0.127 * 9.81 = 1.25$$
 kN/m²

$$\sigma'_A = \sigma_A - u_A = 0$$
 kN/m²

Point B (10 inches): $\sigma_B = H_1\gamma_w + H_2\gamma_{sat} = 1.25 + (0.3302 \times 18.6) = 7.4$ kN/m²

$$u_B = (H_1 + H_2 + h)\gamma_w = (0.127 + 0.3302 + 0.1524)9.81 = 6$$
 kN/m²

$$\sigma'_B = \sigma_B - u_B = 7.4 - 6 = 1.4$$
 kN/m²

Point C (15 inches): $\sigma_c = H_1\gamma_w + z\gamma_{sat} = 1.25 + (0.127 \times 18.6) = 3.61\text{kN/m}^2$

$$u_c = \left(H_1 + z + \frac{h}{H_2} z \right) \gamma_w = \left(0.127 + 0.127 + \frac{0.1524}{0.3302} \times 0.127 \right) 9.81 = 3.1\text{kN/m}^2$$

$$\sigma'_c = \sigma_c - u_c = 3.61 - 3.1 = 0.51\text{ kN/m}^2$$

Depth (m)	Total Pressure (kN/m ²)
0	0
0.127	1.25
0.2545	3.61
0.4572	7.61

Table 14: A table of total pressures along depths

The above data can be further explained by the graph below;

Figure 16: A graph of total pressure along tank depths

Details of this are attached as **Appendix 5**.

When water flow takes place in the soil, upward flow decreases effective stress in the soil. Seepage is the flow of water through the soil and it exerts a frictional drag on the soil particles called seepage force which results in head loss. These seepage forces play a very important role in destabilizing geotechnical structures.

The hydraulic gradient at which the effective stress becomes zero is known as the critical hydraulic gradient.

In the case study of the site conditions; $\sigma' = \gamma H - \gamma_w H = 0$

Under these circumstances, cohesion-less soils could not support any weight imposed by nearby traffic but also the individual weight of the particles themselves which caused slope failure.

As proposed in the methodology, this research was to adapt a subsurface drainage system to drain the soil mass of the amount of water that would provide improved conditions that support the slope sufficiently and the methods initially applied to record positive results for example Geo nailing.

Subsurface drainage is accomplished by placing an artificial conduit or flow path below the water table so the hydraulic head of the conduit is less than that of the soil to be drained (ASCE, 1998). The hydraulic head differential creates a hydraulic gradient towards the flow channel, depressing the phreatic line (also called the free water surface) in the vicinity of the conduit. Water is removed from the conduit at its downstream end, thus maintaining a flow system. It can therefore be seen that subsurface drainage involves principles of hydraulics and flow through porous media. The hydraulic gradient and the hydraulic conductivity of the soil govern the rate of subsurface drainage. (Urban Storm Water Management Manual, 2002)

In evaluating the need to remove subsurface water, consideration must be given to surface water runoff from buildings, road pavements and subgrades, and other impervious surfaces which is allowed to enter subsurface zones and contribute to soil saturation. In clay soils, subsoil drains can alter long-term soil moisture regimes so that building foundations can be adversely affected by removing water, or some cases, by introducing water. In such conditions, subsoil drains should only be used where there are no other options for solving a dampness problem.

Consideration should be given to the possible effects of intermittent or permanent reduction in groundwater levels on adjacent lands when designing subsoil drainage. In soils with clay content exceeding 20%, lowering water tables can cause soil shrinkage and damage to structures. It is recommended that subsoil drains should not be placed too close to buildings on clayey sites. (Urban Storm Water Management Manual, 2002)

A subsurface drainage is a pipe installed beneath the ground surface to collect and /or convey excess water. (Ohio State University, 2010)

4.26 Key considerations during the design

- All drainage works carried out shall comply with the specification to control erosion and sedimentation.
- Adequate provisions for runoff flow at subsurface drainage works shall be made to avoid damage or nuisance due to scour, sedimentation, soil erosion, flooding or diversion of flow.
- Material and equipment shall be located clear of watercourses such that they don't cause damage or danger in the event of large runoff flows. (Liverpool City Council, 1999)
- During the excavation activities, approval from the relevant authority should be obtained since the site neighbors public utilities that may fall within the vicinity of drainage works.
- Trenches shall be excavated to the line, grade, width and depth shown in the drawing and the bottom of the pond shall be constructed such that no localized ponding can occur.
- The excavated material shall be used in construction of embankments backfilling or spoiled in accordance with specification of earthworks.

- Subsurface drainage pipes shall be connected to discharge into gully pits or to outlet structures as directed by the Kampala City Council. As a salinity prevention measure, and where practicable, discharge shall be on a downhill side of the embankment or in the cut-fill area so as to reduce the risk of recharge to the subsurface water table.
- Outlets shall be spaced at a maximum interval of 30m.
- Outlets including those discharging into gully pits shall be made rodent proof using wire nettings to prevent rodents from damaging the geotextile fabric or becoming a hinderance to flow.
- Outlets shall be located so that erosion on the adjacent areas doesn't occur or shall be protected by placement of selected stone.

4.27 Tools

- Perforated corrugated plastic pipes of diameter of 100 mm
- Filter fabric
- Filler material comprising of clean, tough, hard, durable particles

4.28 Cost

The cost is dependent on size of the slope, spacing between the pipes, size of the pipes and cost of the pipes.

4.29 Efficiency

These drains will lower the water table at a rate of 0.5 ft within 24 hours.

The system is as shown in the figure below.

Figure 17: Computer Aided Drawing illustrating the proposed design of subsurface drainage. (Scale: Not Drawn to Scale)

4.30 Materials

a) Geotextile Material

A geotextile lining shall be added to prevent external fine soil particles being washed into the filter material and clogging it. Both this and the unlined rubble drain have only limited effectiveness due to their limited ability to convey water. To understand what particle sizes will be surrounding this system, a particle size distribution test was carried to inform this study on the efficiency and performance of the system.

b) Perforated Pipe

Addition of a pipe to promote more rapid drainage. This is the most common type of subsoil drain. The pipe is perforated to allow easy entry of water and can be rigid or flexible.

The layout will be directly related to the topography, the location of buildings and access points, the geology (nature of subsoil and level of groundwater) and area of a property. Main subsoil drains often follow natural depressions. Subsoil drains shall connect to a stormwater pit or a point of connection, and be consistent with the layouts for the site stormwater drain and the external stormwater drainage network.

4.31 Drain Dimensions and Spacing

The depth of a subsoil drain is dictated by the groundwater conditions, the amount by which the groundwater level is to be lowered, and the available hydraulic gradient. Since the site shall adopt multi-drain systems, the drain spacings given in Table 10 can be used in less critical applications.

From the tests done in Chapters 3 and 4, it's clear that the site contains largely clayey silts, clay soils present particular problems as they may be too impermeable for any drawdown to occur and expert geotechnical advice shall be sought. Trench widths shall be a minimum of 300 mm where circular pipes are used. A minimum width of 450 mm will be required where human access is required. Where a trench is deeper than 1.5 m, shoring as specified by relevant construction safety acts and regulations shall be used.

Drains shall be constructed with the base of the trench at an even slope, so that the trench acts as a rubble drain even if the pipe or geo composite drain is

blocked. Where a subsoil drain pipe or geo composite drain connects to a pit or a pump-out sump, access for easy inspection of flows shall be provided so that the performance of the subsoil drain can be monitored. For drains in critical locations, a means of backflushing should be provided to clear blockages.

Soil Type	Depth (m)	Spacing (m)
Sand	1 -2	50 - 90
Sandy Loam	1 - 1.5	30 - 40
Clayey Silt	0.5 - 1	12 - 16

Table 15: Typical Drainage Spacing (Source: AS/NZ 3500.3.2 (1998))

4.32 Design of Conduits

Pipes or other conduits are often provided in subsoil drains for two purposes: (i) for collection and (ii) for conveyance. A range of geo-composite materials, many of proprietary design, is also available and can be used for the same purpose. Pipes or other conduits associated with subsoil drains shall meet the following requirements:

The size of the conduits is to be related to the expected flows through them. These flows will be very small in fine-grained soils, but will be larger where the drain is located in a pervious stratum such as a sand that is permanently fed by heavy rainfall over a prolonged period.

4.33 Drain Envelopes

Drain envelopes are placed around a subsoil drain such as a pipe, for several purposes. These purposes include (ASCE, 1998);

- To prevent excessive movement of soil material into the drain
- To increase the permeability and hydraulic performance of the material near the subsoil drain
- To increase the effective surface area of the drain

- To stabilize the soil in which the drain is being placed.
- To support and provide structural bedding for the pipe or conduit.

The use of drain envelopes avoids the risk of high hydraulic gradients close to the subsoil drain pipe, which can cause soil instability. It also increases the effectiveness of the drain by increasing its surface area. The material in the drain envelope is often called a filter. (Urban Storm Water Management Manual, 2002)

4.34 Filter Material.

Filter material consisting of natural clean washed sands and gravels and screened crushed rock shall be;

- well graded with a mix of different sizes of sand particles and an adequate permeability
- with natural sand, less than 5% passing a 75 μm sieve
- screened crushed rock, sizes 3 mm to 20 mm
- sufficiently coarse not to wash into the subsoil drain, or through pores in a geotextile cover to such drain.
- chemically stable and inert to possible actions of soil and groundwater.

4.35 Geotextile Filter

The permeability of geotextiles used in subsoil drains should be greater than that of the native soil. The following general requirements shall be considered; a desirable permeability for geotextiles is 10 times that of the native soil, there is a tendency for geotextiles to clog at some locations, particularly where iron salts are present, e.g. scoria. Oxidation and biologically related actions can cause plate-like deposits of ferruginous particles on filter surfaces, rapidly clogging them. In such areas, carefully selected granular filters should be used instead of geotextiles.

Advice from a professional engineer with geotechnical expertise should be sought in such situations. (Urban Storm Water Management Manual, 2002)

4.36 Installation.

Any pipes, conduits and fittings in such drains shall be cleaned internally prior to installation and commissioning, continuously supported by embedment jointed with elastomeric seals, solvent cement or joints complying with the manufacturer's recommendations and/or requirements of the Local Authority.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study achieved all the objectives set for the study of the parameters identified. For objective 1, the study found that mechanical properties of a soil sample are primary in determination of stability of a slope during construction. The study however did not exhaust all the parameters and further research into how other properties (that are not discussed in this study) affect slope stability, should be conducted.

It was evident through the review of secondary data in the geotechnical report annexed that major mechanical properties of soil were studied during the initial

project phase for soil tests but the rise in water table as a result of exerted horizontal loads from the adjacent building and contribution of heavy rainfall patterns that facilitated high seepage volumes was not considered.

Objective 2 of the study informed that the amount of ground water directly affects soil stability. The higher the amount of groundwater, the lower the stability of the slope. The contribution of the seepage due to intense rainfall patterns received worsened slope condition by reducing the factor of safety.

This required an underground drainage system based on objective three to drain the water out and improve the soil conditions.

This research has answered the question of the influence of water table on slope stability and to what extent may a water table affect construction works depending on the soil conditions. The research makes several recommendations for further research areas due to limitations in time and scope.

5.1 Recommendations

- i. Mitigation for rise in groundwater level is important for risk assessment in slope stability analysis and therefore should be observed. Research into water table rise modeling is encouraged.
- ii. Soil Nailing as a means of slope stabilization mechanism is not efficient in very wet soils because the angle of friction is compromised. The use of sheet piles is therefore encouraged.

- iii. Exercise safety for deep excavations near built environments and public goods like roads, all roads should within 10 m of the site should be closed off with proper cost and effect considerations incurred in diverted traffic.
- iv. More research should be done on underground drainage systems to check their compliance with water amounts and soil type classifications.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1 - PICTORIAL LOGS FOR CURRENT SITE CONDITIONS

Photo 1: Excavated soil slopes

Photo 2: Slope underground reinforcements

Photo 3: Collapsed soil masses

Photo 4: Failed Geo Nailing

Photo 5: Delayed construction works

Photo 6: Accumulation of underground water

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LABORATORY WORKS

Photo 1: Weighing soil sample in lab.

Photo 2: Sample preparation in the lab

Photo 3: Data Recording in the lab

Photo 4: Failure samples TP 1

Photo 5: Failure samples TP 2

Photo 6: Failure sample TP 3

APPENDIX 2- CONSOLIDATION DATA ANALYSIS

BH No.	Depth (m)	MC (%)	LL	Cc (Terzhagi and Peck 1948)	Cc (Herrero 1983)
	1.50	27.2	34.8	0.2232	0.19651
	3.00	27.0	33.9	0.2151	0.19451
	4.50	22.6	34.1	0.2169	0.15051
	6.00	25.0	33.2	0.2088	0.17451
BH 1	7.50	25.8	25.3	0.1377	0.18251
	9.00	26.9	65.4	0.4986	0.19351
	10.50	24.8	57.8	0.4302	0.17251
	12.00	37.3	44	0.306	0.29751
	13.50	39.5	33	0.207	0.31951
	15.00	27.0	31.2	0.1908	0.19451
	16.50	26.3	29.4	0.1746	0.18751
	18.00	17.1	26	0.144	0.09551
	19.50	23.8	28.4	0.1656	0.16251
	1.50	29.6	39.9	0.2691	0.22051
	3.00	26.1	38.8	0.2592	0.18551
	4.50	25.4	41.8	0.2862	0.17851
	6.00	27.2	47.9	0.3411	0.19651
	7.50	31.7	60.3	0.4527	0.24151
	9.00	40.2	61.8	0.4662	0.32651
BH 2	10.50	38.3	63.3	0.4797	0.30751
	12.00	41.3	57.3	0.4257	0.33751
	13.50	28.6	49.3	0.3537	0.21051
	15.00	38.8	59.9	0.4491	0.31251
	16.50	30.3	49.8	0.3582	0.22751
	18.00	32.9	49.9	0.3591	0.25351
	19.50	24.5	39.9	0.2691	0.16951

A graph showing Compression Index along different depth

Compression Index versus MC (Herrero 1983)

APPENDIX 3- SPT DATA ANALYSIS

BH No.	Depth (m)	Predominant Soil Fraction	Measured SPT 'N' Value	Corrected SPT 'N' Value	Allowable Bearing Capacity By Terzaghi and Peck 1948	Allowable Bearing Capacity Terzaghi and Peck, (1967)	Bearing Capacity Factor Nc	FoS	K	Unconfined Comprehensive strength Qu (Kpa)	Cohesion Cu	Qult (kPa)	Qall
			N	N _{COR}									
BH01	1.5	Clayey Silts	10	<u>8</u>	75	84	5.14	3	13.27	106.16	53.08	272.83	90.94
	3		10	<u>8</u>	75	84	5.14	3	13.27	106.16	53.08	272.83	90.94
	4.5		12	<u>10</u>	102	114	5.14	3	13.27	132.7	66.35	341.04	113.68
	6		17	<u>14</u>	145	161	5.14	3	13.27	185.78	92.89	477.45	159.15
	7.5	Silty Clay	>60	<u>>60</u>	>600	601	5.14	3	13.27	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
	9	Clayey Silts	15	<u>14</u>	143	159	5.14	3	13.27	185.78	92.89	477.45	159.15
	10.5	Sandy Silts	9	<u>8</u>	82	92	5.14	3	13.27	106.16	53.08	272.83	90.94
	12		39	<u>34</u>	340	378	5.14	3	13.27	451.18	225.59	1159.53	386.51
	13.5		38	<u>32</u>	317	500	5.14	3	13.27	424.64	212.32	1091.32	363.77
	15		>60	<u>>60</u>	>600	601	5.14	3	13.27	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
	16.5	Silty Sands	>60	<u>>60</u>	6	601	5.14	3	13.27	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
	18		47	<u>31</u>	390	390	5.14	3	13.27	411.37	205.685	1057.22	352.41
19.5	47		<u>31</u>	390	390	5.14	3	13.27	411.37	205.685	1057.22	352.41	
1.5	Clayey Silts		8	<u>6</u>	60	67	5.14	3	13.27	79.62	39.81	204.62	68.21
3		8	<u>6</u>	60	67	5.14	3	13.27	79.62	39.81	204.62	68.21	
4.5		27	<u>23</u>	230	256	5.14	3	13.27	305.21	152.605	784.39	261.46	
6		30	<u>23</u>	255	210	5.14	3	13.27	305.21	152.605	784.39	261.46	
7.5	Silty Clay	28	<u>27</u>	266	296	5.14	3	13.27	358.29	179.145	920.81	306.94	
9	Clayey Silts	31	<u>29</u>	295	328	5.14	3	13.27	384.83	192.415	989.01	329.67	
10.5	Sandy Silts	10	<u>9</u>	92	102	5.14	3	13.27	119.43	59.715	306.94	102.31	
12		18	<u>16</u>	158	175	5.14	3	13.27	212.32	106.16	545.66	181.89	
13.5		41	<u>28</u>	350	350	5.14	3	13.27	371.56	185.78	954.91	318.30	
15		25	<u>20</u>	202	225	5.14	3	13.27	265.4	132.7	682.08	227.36	
16.5	Silty Sands	36	<u>28</u>	282	314	5.14	3	13.27	371.56	185.78	954.91	318.30	
18		46	<u>35</u>	351	391	5.14	3	13.27	464.45	232.225	1193.64	397.88	
19.5		52	<u>39</u>	387	431	5.14	3	13.27	517.53	258.765	1330.05	443.35	

A graph showing the differences in Qall along different depths (Terzaghi & peck, 1967).

APPENDIX 4 - SOIL CLASSIFICATION ANALYSIS

BH No.	Depth (m)	PD	Plasticity				USCS	MC	Bulk Density	Unit Weight	% Passing Sieve (mm)															
			LL	PL	PI	LS					75.0	50.0	37.5	20.0	10.0	6.3	5.0	2.0	1.18	0.600	0.425	0.300	0.212	0.150	0.075	
	1.5-2.0	Clayey Silt	34.8	26.2	28.0	14.0	MH	27.2	1.823	17.9	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	97	96	95	95	94	92	90	
	2.0-3.5		33.9	29.2	24.7	12.9	MH	27.0	2.132	20.9	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	97	96	95	94	94	93	92	89
	4.5-5.0		34.4	30.5	23.9	13.2	MH	22.6	1.988	19.3	100	100	100	100	100	99	96	89	87	85	83	83	83	82	80	
	6.0-6.5		33.2	27.2	26.1	12.5	MH	25.8	2.033	20.1	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	98	97	96	95	95	93	94	92	
	7.5-8.0		Silty Clay	25.3	11.4	13.9	7.4	CL	26.9	2.213	21.7	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	99	98	98	97	96	93
BH 1	9.0-9.5	Silty Clay	65.4	37.1	28.3	15.4	MH	24.8	2.150	21.1	100	100	100	100	100	97	97	95	94	94	93	93	91	89	86	
	10.5-11.0		57.8	29.4	28.4	14.8	MH	37.3	1.955	19.2	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	99	99	99	98	98	96	
	12.0-12.5	Sandy silts	44.0	36.9	7.2	2.4	ML	39.5	1.983	19.5	100	100	100	88	88	88	88	88	88	87	81	81	79	71	54	
	13.5-14.0		33.0	25.5	7.5	19.0	ML	27.0	1.872	18.3	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	96	96	91	73	53	
	15.0-15.5	Clay sands	31.2	18.5	12.3	3.2	SC	26.3	1.964	19.2	100	100	100	100	98	98	98	97	97	93	94	94	88	73	49	
	16.5-17.5	Silty Sands	29.4	23.3	6.1	2.0	SM	17.1	2.205	21.6	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	98	93	76	44	
	18.0-18.5		26.0	19.8	6.1	2.3	SM	13.1	2.192	21.5	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	96	96	84	60	36	
	19.5-20.0		28.4	20.9	7.5	3.0	SM	23.8	2.678	20.4	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	92	97	93	76	49	
	1.5-2.0	Clay Silts	39.9	33.8	26.1	14.1	MH	29.6	1.913	18.7	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	92	96	96	95	93	91	
	3.0-3.5		38.8	33.7	25.0	13.5	MH	26.1	1.960	19.2	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	97	95	94	93	92	91	89	87
	4.5-5.0		41.8	25.8	15.9	8.2	ML	25.4	1.877	18.4	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	97	96	93	94	93	92	90
	6.0-6.5		47.9	28.3	39.6	12.6	ML	27.2	1.977	19.4	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	96	95	95	94	93	92	
	7.5-8.0		Silty Sands	66.3	32.3	28.2	11.6	SM	31.6	1.894	18.6	100	100	100	100	74	68	63	53	47	41	38	33	32	28	25
	9.0-9.5	Silty Clay	61.8	28.3	33.5	11.2	CH	40.2	1.865	18.3	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	89	99	99	98	98	97	
	10.5-11.0	Clay Silts	62.3	35.0	40.3	8.8	MH	38.3	1.294	12.6	100	100	100	100	100	98	97	93	91	90	89	88	87	85	82	
	12.0-12.5		57.5	42.0	16.0	7.7	MH	41.7	1.845	18.1	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	98	98	95	94	93	92	89	85
BH 2	13.5-14.0		Silty sands	49.3	35.3	14.2	8.4	SM	20.6	2.040	20.0	100	100	100	100	92	81	77	61	55	48	46	43	40	36	32
	15.0-15.5	Clayey Silts	50.9	35.5	13.4	5.4	MH	38.8	1.944	19.1	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	97	92	
	16.5-17.0		49.8	37.3	5.1	4.6	ML	30.3	2.022	19.8	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	98	98	97	97	96	91	89	76	
	18.0-18.5		49.9	37.6	13.0	7.4	ML	32.9	2.088	20.4	100	100	100	100	100	98	95	99	93	93	93	92	91	85	75	
	18.5-20.0		39.9	36.3	13.5	3.3	ML	24.5	2.432	20.5	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	99	98	98	97	95	89	78

APPENDIX 5 -SEEPAGE FLOW DATA ANALYSIS

Depth	Total Pressure
0	0
0.127	1.25
0.2545	3.61
0.4572	7.61

